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Compass

PLATFORM TOOLKIT

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1. The Compass Project

The project "Compass - orientating you towards your best international mobility choice" aims to provide comprehensive and inclusive support to students across Europe who are seeking a mobility experience abroad. Recognizing the challenges faced by students from diverse social and cultural backgrounds in accessing information and opportunities, the project seeks to bridge the gap by offering a high-quality support system.

At the heart of the Compass project is an online platform that incorporates an automated matching system. This tool will assist students in finding the most suitable academic path and provide guidance and support during the orientation and preparation phase of their mobility journey. By facilitating easier access to quality information and fostering collaborations between students, associations, and Higher Education Institutions, the project aims to ensure that students receive the support they need throughout the process. To do so, the COMPASS project has three main objectives:

- Improving support during the orientation and preparation phase through an online matching tool for students who are organising their mobility;
- Fostering the internationalisation of universities and local students associations by promoting dialogue, open-mindedness and mutual understanding – tools for European citizenship;
- Strengthening the support structures for mobile students and helping them reinforce the existing practices as well as develop sustainable relationships between key stakeholders.

To achieve these objectives, the Compass consortium, led by the Erasmus Student Network (ESN) France, the project coordinator, Erasmus Student Network International, Erasmus Student Network Italy, the European University Foundation, the University of Hertfordshire and the University of Vienna, will provide common pedagogical tools and establish a platform for sharing support practices.

This toolkit was developed to support International Relation Officers and International Student Organisations to assist young people prepare for their mobility journeys abroad. As these two actors are often the main source of information for these young people, it is essential that they may find resources to support their work. The first part of this toolkit is a guide to reach out to students preparing for mobility, the second part is a guide to reach out to students returning from one, and the third part is a guide for recruiting students to become ambassadors of the platform.

2. Presenting the Compass Platform

Whether you are working in the International Relations Office of a university or a Student Organisation, if your goal is to enhance international mobility and support young people in the preparation stages of their mobility, the Compass platform is the peer-to-peer tool to help you connect them with students returning from mobility. Below, you can find an easy step-by-step guide to presenting the platform.

Compass Platform Guidelines

Steps to follow to insert a contribution on the *Compass* platform:

The platform is entirely in English, so you will need to write your posts in **English!**

1. Register and log in: by clicking on “sign up” at the top right of the page, you will be able to create an account. You will have to remember to go to your mailbox to validate your registration and **login with your email and password.**

[Home](#)

[Search](#)

[Contact us](#)

[Log in](#)

[Sign up](#)

2. Create your profile: once connected, you will have access to your profile by clicking on your first name at the top right of the page.

As soon as you create your profile, you will be asked to confirm it by clicking a link sent to your email address.

You can now edit your profile. You can also decide to share your social networks and allow users to contact you directly to exchange information and get more tips about international mobility!

You will have to choose the country, the city and the university where you studied by clicking on "*Manage education*". The period in which mobility takes or took place is also mandatory.

Manage schools

[Return to the profile](#)

Start ↓	End	Location	School name	As a local	Actions
---------	-----	----------	-------------	------------	---------

[Add a education to the list](#)

Be careful, this platform only allows you to add contributions at the European level. You can, however, indicate if you have ever done a mobility program outside Europe.

3. Insert a contribution by writing a post:

Once your profile is created, you can share your experience! If you have filled in everything correctly beforehand, some questions can guide you and give you ideas for themes.

Share your experience!

[Cancel and return to your profile](#)

You studied in Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon

How can disabled students can find help for their specific needs (accommodation, transportation etc...) in Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon?

What was the most remarkable cultural or historial spot of Athína for you?

Was the cost of living in Greece accessible for you?

Others subjects :

[#studentlife](#)

[#admin](#)

[#culture](#)

[#transportation](#)

[#finance](#)

[#food](#)

[#health](#)

[#leisure](#)

[#weather](#)

[#accommodation](#)

[#goingout](#)

[#accessibility](#)

You are free to post whatever you prefer, without clicking on a question, but in this case, you have to choose a tag and decide if you want to post about: the university, the city or the country (it can't be all three at the same time).

In any case, **don't forget to add tags** to allow users to easily find your posts. So that everyone can find and understand more easily what you wrote.

Add post

Cancel and return

Subject

Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon

Title

Universty life and the canteen

Content

Tags

× studentlife

Create

4. Tips:

- **The more information you write the more satisfying and useful your contribution will be** to the reader. However, since you can also write more than one contribution, **try to differentiate per topic or tag** if you feel that you have a lot to share or talk about, so the contribution is not too long to read or complex to find.
- **Don't hesitate to make references to concrete things** such as addresses or opening hours of a university office or, on the other hand, to point out a place or a thing to avoid (e.g. certain neighbourhoods to avoid at night or that are too expensive for housing).
- It would be perfect if you included some **practical advice** at the end of your contribution.
- **If you feel like it, add your social media accounts**, so that users can get in touch to have further details and exchange information (and even let you know how much you contributed to improving their mobility experience!)

How can all actors be engaged to ensure the Compass platform benefits all mobility players?

3. Promoting the Compass Platform to Outgoing Students

Students who are preparing for international mobility are always filled with enthusiasm to gather as much information as possible about the opportunities available to them. That's where the Compass platform comes in - to assist them in navigating and preparing for their journey abroad. With the following resources at your disposal, you can communicate about the Compass platform effectively. These resources include ready-to-use templates for emails, social media posts, website articles, and even flyers. While these resources are already prepared for immediate use, they can also be customized to suit your local context and language preferences.

3.1 Timeline for Communication

The communication around the Compass platform should happen **at the beginning of every semester**, in February-March and September-October.

The purpose of the Compass platform is to assist students in choosing their mobility destination, before submitting their application to the HEI. Ideally, the Compass platform will be introduced by you together with the available mobility opportunities, as an additional tool to help with their mobility journey.

It is recommended to include references to the Compass platform from the early stages of the mobility application process until the students have to formally confirm their destination, in order to assure they make an informed decision.

3.2 Promoting the Compass Platform via Email

Subject: Finding all information regarding your mobility on the Compass Platform

Text: Dear Students,

When preparing for international student mobility, it is important to be as informed as possible regarding all aspects of your experience. Where to find accommodation, what is student life like in your destination, which courses you should take, what kind of student organisations you can find there...

Luckily, there is one website you can visit to find all the information you may need. The Compass Platform, developed in the framework of the Compass Project, gathers testimonials from students returning from their mobility journeys.

 What is this platform for?

This platform **allows students who are preparing for their mobility to get information** and prepare themselves thanks to the testimonies of other students.

👤 For whom? If you are planning to experience international mobility and need more insight into what it means and get more information about a country, a city or a higher education institution.

🤔 How? By visiting the platform, reading, reacting and commenting on the testimonies!

To do this, you need to visit <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>. If you have any comments, questions or suggestions, you can contact the team moderating the platform at the following e-mail address: contact@compass-youthmobility.eu

If you need further information about the project you can check <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project>

Kind regards,

Sender

Email visual:

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.3 Promoting the Compass Platform with an Article on Your Website

Headline: The Compass Platform: an Informative Tool for Your Mobility

Article visual:

Text:

The Compass project aims at helping students prepare for their mobility by putting them in contact with students who have already gone abroad or with local students at the desired institution or destination. To connect international students with locals, the project consortium co-created a tool: the Compass platform. You can visit it at: <https://compass-youthmobility.eu>.

The platform allows students that have already experienced international mobility to post testimonials about the country, city or university they went to. To publish testimonies the platform suggests tags on various subjects, such as #leisure #goingout #accommodation #culture #food #accessibility #weather #health #finance. Indeed, the aim is to improve guidance and preparation through an online tool for students preparing for mobility.

The project also allows the structures supporting students in mobility (universities and associations) to strengthen their practices and develop sustainable relationships by providing them with common and inclusive educational tools.

Why do we believe in peer-to-peer feedback?

- It eases the mind of those going on international mobility
- There exists higher trustworthiness between students
- Students provide more convincing feedback
- It is a first-hand real-life experience
- International offices do not usually manage information about housing and local experience

Whether you are currently deciding on going abroad for your studies and need convincing or reassuring, or whether you have experienced international mobility and wish for people to have such a colourful experience as you did, let's meet at <https://compass-youthmobility.eu>.

If you want to know more about the project, we suggest you go check this other page: <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project/resources> where you can find two studies about the needs of students in preparing for international mobility as well as the stakeholder's point of view. A guide of good practices is also available if you want to know more about peer-to-peer and how it can help in preparing for international mobility!

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.4 Promoting the Compass Platform on Social Media

Text to use on all platforms:

Are you planning to go on mobility abroad and wondering what your life will be like there? Are you looking for accommodation? Are you searching for the best courses to follow? Go visit the Compass Platform to find out all the information directly from students who have been in your shoes!

 What is this platform for?

This platform **allows students who are preparing for their mobility to get information** and prepare themselves thanks to the testimonies of other students.

 For whom? If you are planning to experience international mobility and need more insight into what it means and get more information about a country, a city or a higher education institution.

 How? By visiting the platform, reading, reacting and commenting on the testimonies!

To do this, you need to visit <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>. If you have any comments, questions or suggestions, you can contact us at the following e-mail address:

contact@compass-youthmobility.eu

If you need further information about the project you can check

<https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project>

3.4.1 Promotion on Facebook

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.4.2 Promotion on LinkedIn

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ARE YOU PREPARING FOR
INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY? DO YOU
WANT TO GET INFORMATION ABOUT THE
COUNTRY OR THE UNIVERSITY?

YOU NEED TO VISIT: [COMPASS-YOUTHMOBILITY.EU](https://compass-youthmobility.eu)

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.4.3 Promotion on Instagram

Co-funded by
the European Union

Compass

ARE YOU PREPARING FOR
INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY? DO YOU
WANT TO GET INFORMATION ABOUT THE
COUNTRY OR THE UNIVERSITY?

YOU NEED TO VISIT: [COMPASS-YOUTHMOBILITY.EU](https://compass-youthmobility.eu)

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.4.4 Promotion on Instagram Stories

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

3.5 Promoting the Compass Platform with a Flyer

Co-funded by
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Compass

ARE YOU PREPARING FOR
INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY ? DO
YOU WANT TO GET INFORMATION
ABOUT THE COUNTRY OR THE
UNIVERSITY ? YOU NEED TO VISIT

compass-youthmobility.eu

AND GET LOTS OF DIFFERENT TIPS
FROM OTHER STUDENTS

FURTHER INFORMATION ABOUT THE PROJECT ON THIS WEBSITE:

compass-youthmobility.eu/project

“Through her testimony, Marion convinced me that flatsharing is the best option for me !” #Compass

“Thanks to Léa, I know how to get around in Granada ! #Compass

“Thanks to Valentine, I know how I can make new friends : in ESN Torino ! #Compass

“Thanks to Tiphaine, I am thinking of going on mobility in the Netherlands, it seems awesome! #Compass

The template for the visuals can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4. Promoting the Compass Platform to Students Returning from Mobility

Students who have recently returned from international mobility experiences can provide a wealth of valuable information to their peers. They have firsthand knowledge of what their fellow students are seeking and are often eager to share their insights and experiences. These returning students can serve as invaluable resources, offering advice on what worked well for them during their time abroad and what they wish they had known before embarking on their journeys.

To tap into this valuable resource, we have developed the resources below that will help you motivate these returning students to share their tips and advice on the platform. By following these suggestions, you can encourage them to contribute their valuable knowledge and help create a vibrant community of information exchange.

4.1 Timeline for Communication

The communication around the Compass platform should happen **at the end of every semester**, in January-February and June-July.

The purpose of the Compass platform is to assist students in choosing their mobility destination, based on the experience of former mobility students. For the platform to continue to be supportive of outgoing students, current and freshly-returning students must share their tips, tricks and recommendations, as well as be reachable.

Ideally, returning students would be reminded to share their experiences on the Compass platform before they finalise their mobility. It is recommended to include reminders about the Compass platform together with their final administrative requirements.

4.2 Promoting the Compass Platform via Email

Subject: Help Students Find Their Mobility Destination!

Text: Dear Students,

You have recently returned from a mobility experience abroad, and we now need your help helping another generation of students experience this unique journey. Did you know that the Compass Platform is there to help you share tips about your mobility?

 What is this platform for?

This platform allows students who are preparing for their mobility to get information and prepare themselves **thanks to the testimonies of other students**.

 For whom? We need help from students who have already experienced international mobility or that are currently abroad.

 How? By writing testimonials for other students to read and get inspired to study in Europe! The content can be about the country, the city or the university on many different topics: food, museums, outdoor activities, courses etc... The aim is to help students get a better idea of what to expect during their mobility.

To do this, you need to create your account at <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>. If you have any comments, questions or suggestions, you can contact us at the following e-mail address: contact@compass-youthmobility.eu

If you need further information about the project you can check <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project>

Looking forward to reading all your beautiful testimonials!

Sender

Visual:

The template for the visuals can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4.3 Promoting the Compass Platform on Social Media

Text to use on all platforms:

Are you coming back from international mobility? Come share your tips on the Compass Platform!

 What is this platform for?

This platform allows students who are preparing for their mobility to get information and prepare themselves **thanks to the testimonies of other students**.

 For whom? We need help from students who have already experienced international mobility or that are currently abroad.

 How? By writing testimonials for other students to read and get inspired to study in Europe! The content can be about the country, the city or the university on many different topics: food, museums, outdoor activities, courses etc... The aim is to help students get a better idea of what to expect during their mobility.

To do this, you need to create your account at <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>. If you have any comments, questions or suggestions, you can contact us at the following e-mail address: contact@compass-youthmobility.eu

If you need further information about the project you can check <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project>

4.3.1 Promotion on Facebook

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4.3.2 Promotion on LinkedIn

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**HAVE YOU GONE ABROAD FOR
YOUR STUDIES? DO YOU WANT TO
HELP OTHER STUDENTS TO
PREPARE THEIR OWN EXPERIENCE
OF INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY?**

**GO REGISTER ON
compass-youthmobility.eu**

Compass

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4.3.3 Promotion on Instagram

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4.3.4 Promotion on Instagram Stories

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

4.3 Promoting the Compass Platform with a Flyer

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**HAVE YOU GONE ABROAD FOR
YOUR STUDIES? DO YOU WANT TO
HELP OTHER STUDENTS TO
PREPARE THEIR OWN EXPERIENCE
OF INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY?**

Go register on
compass-youthmobility.eu
and follow the process!

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the European Union

Compass

**HAVE YOU GONE ABROAD FOR
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HELP OTHER STUDENTS TO
PREPARE THEIR OWN EXPERIENCE
OF INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY?**

Go register on
compass-youthmobility.eu
and follow the process!

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

5. Recruiting Ambassadors to promote the Compass Platform

This next part is designed for IRO university staff eager to further promote the Compass platform among students. To ensure that students are well-informed about the platform and understand how it can help them find the information they need or share the information they have, one effective strategy is to recruit student ambassadors.

These ambassadors can play a vital role in promoting the platform to their peers, especially those who are actively involved in student organizations or have recently returned from mobility programs and are enthusiastic about motivating other students to utilize the platform. This approach can greatly contribute to the overall success and increased adoption of the Compass platform among the student community. The tools below will help you connect with these ambassadors.

5.1 Promoting the Compass Platform Social Media

Text to use on all platforms:

Are you interested in helping students get ready for their international mobility? Join us and become an ambassador of the Compass Platform!

 What is this platform for?

The Compass Platform is designed to assist students who are preparing for international mobility by providing them with valuable information and guidance through testimonials of other students.

 For whom? We seek assistance from young people who have experienced international mobility and who want to promote it.

 How? Communicate with students who are preparing for their mobility and show them how they can use the Compass platform to find information and get connected with students coming back from abroad.

To participate, simply create an account at <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>. If you have any comments, questions, or suggestions, feel free to reach out to us via email at contact@compass-youthmobility.eu.

For more information about the project, please visit <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project>.

5.1.1 Promotion on Facebook

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

5.1.2 Promotion on LinkedIn

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

5.1.3 Promotion on Instagram

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

5.1.4 Promotion on Instagram Stories

The template for the visual can be found [on this link](#). Feel free to update them according to your local context.

5.2 Promoting the Compass Platform with a Flyer

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The Compass platform is helping students make a choice for their future: which country or university should they pick? The Compass platform reassures students: where to meet new people? What is student life like in other European countries? If you want to help students interact and make mobility an opportunity for all, join the Ambassador's team!

Further information about the project on this website:
compass-youthmobility.eu/project

6. Promoting the Compass Platform to HEI staff

This next part is dedicated to Student Organisations who are wishing to implement the Compass platform within their own universities and wish to get in touch with the International Relations Office staff to explain to them what is the platform and how it can be an improvement in their work of preparing students for mobility. Below is an email template that can be sent to HEI staff.

Email Template:

What is the Compass project?

The Compass project aims at helping students prepare for their mobility by putting them in contact with other students who are currently experiencing or have already undertaken international mobility. Besides the platform, you will also be able to explore research results on the needs of students at different stages of the mobility process, the practices of stakeholders involved in mobility preparation, a best practices guide to improve support to students going on mobility, a training kit on how to use the platform and a recommendation booklet.

What is this platform for?

This Platform developed by ESN France with ESN International, ESN Italy, EUF, the University of Vienna and the University of Hertfordshire enables students to prepare their mobility to get informed and prepared through the testimonies of others!

How can it be useful to Higher Education Institutions?

Throughout the research on stakeholders' practices to support students going on mobility, a common issue was that International Officers struggle to convey information about the mobility experience and the actual details of their destination. This tool provides a peer-to-peer experience to students which is more convincing, creates a bridge between countries and higher education institutions and conveys higher trustworthiness. The compass platform eases the minds of students planning to go abroad by providing information about local experiences that can be sometimes put aside by higher education institutions due to a lack of resources and time.

The first version of the Compass platform is ready! You can go check it out at <https://compass-youthmobility.eu/>

What can you do as Higher Education institution?

- You can start sharing with students preparing for their international mobility! They will find useful information on the platform that will certainly allow them to better prepare (and get excited) about their mobility destination!
- You can share it with students that are currently experiencing international mobility and students back from mobility. They can then share their feedback on the platform and give back to the others that are still considering going, as by reading testimonies from other students they will get inspired to study abroad! The goal is to have as many participants involved on the platform so we have as many different perspectives as possible, as well as destinations covered. The content can be about the country, the city or the university, food, museums, outdoor activities, courses etc. The goal is to help students get a better idea of what is waiting for them on their international mobility.

You will also find on the platform website a **Study Report regarding the expectations and needs of students preparing for international mobility.**

<https://compass-youthmobility.eu/project/resources>.

Thank you for reading me,

Sender

The Compass project was co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Commission, under Key Action 2 from the French National Agency for Education and Training.

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute the endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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